

AMOUNT OF AMMONIFIERS AND THEIR SEASONAL DYNAMICS IN SOILS WITH DIFFERENT SALINITY LEVELS (CASE STUDY OF MIRZAOBOD DISTRICT)

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ABSTRACT

This article presents data on the abundance of ammonifiers and their seasonal dynamics in soils of varying salinity levels within the “Mustaqillik” massif of the Mirzaobod district. The study describes how the number of ammonifiers changes under the influence of soil salinization processes, crop types, and seasonal environmental factors

Introduction

Microorganisms play a significant role among the key factors that maintain the natural ecological balance and govern the biogenic migration of atoms in the environment. Therefore, studying the dynamics of soil microflora and managing these processes is of great importance in agronomy, ecology, and biotechnology.

The decomposition of nitrogen-containing organic compounds in soil to ammonia is directly associated with the activity of ammonifying bacteria. These microorganisms hold an essential position in the cyclic nitrogen turnover within the biosphere. It is well established that ammonifying bacteria constitute one of the most widespread groups of microorganisms in soils.

Materials and Methods

During the study, soil samples were collected from the plow layer and sub-plow layer to determine the number of microorganisms present in the research area. Microbiological analysis of the soil was carried out using standard methods commonly applied in soil microbiology. According to these methods, ammonifying bacteria were cultured and quantified on a meat-peptone agar (MPA) nutrient medium.

Results and Discussion

The results of microbiological analyses conducted to assess the abundance of microorganisms in the soils of the study area indicate that ammonifiers represent the dominant microbial group. In Profile No. 1, their population in the topsoil layer (0–33 cm) reached 4.7×10^6 CFU/g in spring, 2.2×10^6 CFU/g in summer, and 3.3×10^6 CFU/g in autumn. In the subsurface layer (33–56 cm), the number of ammonifiers decreased in accordance with the lower humus content and reduced availability of nutrients, amounting to 2.1×10^5 CFU/g in spring, 1.2×10^5 CFU/g in summer, and 1.6×10^5 CFU/g in autumn.

Table 1
Abundance of ammonifiers in soils, CFU/g soil
(colony-forming units per 1 g soil)

Profile No.	Layer depth, cm	Crop type	Salinity level	Seasons		
				Spring	Summer	Autumn
1	0-33	Medicago	slightly saline	4,7x10 ⁶	2,2x10 ⁶	3,3x10 ⁶
	33-56		slightly saline	2,1x10 ⁵	1,2x10 ⁵	1,6x10 ⁵
24	0-32	Triticum	moderately saline	1,9x10 ⁵	1,1x10 ⁵	1,5x10 ⁵
	32-55		strongly saline	8x10 ⁴	2,2x10 ⁴	4,5x10 ⁴
29	0-29	Cucumis melo	slightly saline	2,7x10 ⁶	1,5x10 ⁶	2,1x10 ⁶
	29-53		slightly saline	1,6x10 ⁵	1,2x10 ⁵	1,4x10 ⁵
68	0-31	Zea mays	non-saline	8,7x10 ⁶	3,0x10 ⁶	4,3x10 ⁶
	31-52		non-saline	6,7x10 ⁶	1,8x10 ⁶	3,5x10 ⁶

Analysis of profile No. 24 shows that in the 0–32 cm soil layer, the population of ammonifying microorganisms reaches 1.9×10^5 CFU/g in spring, 1.1×10^5 CFU/g in summer, and 1.5×10^5 CFU/g in autumn. In the subsurface layer (32–55 cm), their abundance decreases to 8×10^4 CFU/g in spring, 2.2×10^4 CFU/g in summer, and 4.5×10^4 CFU/g in autumn.

In profile No. 29, the amount of ammonifiers in the 0–29 cm layer reaches 2.7×10^6 CFU/g in spring, 1.5×10^6 CFU/g in summer, and 2.1×10^6 CFU/g in autumn. In the 29–53 cm subsurface horizon, their population is 1.6×10^5 CFU/g in spring, 1.2×10^5 CFU/g in summer, and 1.4×10^5 CFU/g in autumn.

The study revealed that the highest concentrations of ammonifying microorganisms occur in profile No. 68. In the plow layer, their abundance reaches 8.7×10^6 CFU/g in spring, 3×10^6 CFU/g in summer, and 4.3×10^6 CFU/g in autumn. In the subsurface soil layer (31–52 cm), the ammonifier population amounts to 6.7×10^6 CFU/g in spring, 1.8×10^6 CFU/g in summer, and 3.5×10^6 CFU/g in autumn.

Figure 1. Seasonal dynamics of ammonifier abundance in soils.

It is well established that microorganisms serve as highly sensitive indicators of changes in soil–ecological conditions. One of the major limiting factors for the development of ammonifying microorganisms in the studied soils is the varying degree of soil salinity. Accordingly, the highest abundance of ammonifiers is observed in non-saline soils, whereas increasing salinity levels lead to a marked decline in their population. Our research demonstrated that a rise in soil salinity results in a significant reduction in the total number of microorganisms.

Seasonal dynamics of ammonifiers exhibit a distinct pattern. Their maximum abundance occurs in spring, followed by a notable decrease in summer, and a partial increase in autumn; however, their numbers do not reach spring levels. In the analyzed soil samples, ammonifying bacteria belonging to the genera *Bacillus*, *Micrococcus*, and *Clostridium* were identified.

Overall, ammonifier activity peaks in spring, decreases in summer, and partially recovers in autumn. These trends are closely associated with soil moisture, temperature regimes, and the physiological activity of plant roots. Therefore, the high abundance of ammonifiers serves as an important indicator of soil biological activity and its fertility status.

Conclusions

The study demonstrated that the abundance of ammonifying bacteria in the examined soils is directly influenced by soil salinity level, crop type, and seasonal factors. The results indicate that in all soil profiles the highest number of ammonifiers occurs in the plow layer, with a gradual decline in the subsoil horizons. This is attributed to the higher content of humus, greater availability of nutrients, and more favorable aeration conditions in the upper soil layers. The maximum abundance of ammonifiers was observed in non-saline soils, while the lowest values occurred in strongly saline soils.

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